

THM@Sim4IA'25

TH Mittelhessen & Herder Institute

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<https://sim4ia.org/sigir2025>

Overview

- 4 student assistants
- Participation in all 3 tasks
- Manual and automatic runs
- No usage of Docker, SimlIR 3.0 or training data
- Usage of small labelling tool to help with manual annotations and re-running automatic runs
- Code on GitHub

The screenshot shows a Jupyter Notebook window titled 'task_b.ipynb'. The interface includes a toolbar with buttons for 'Generieren', '+ Code', '+ Markdown', 'Unterbrechen', and 'Neu starten'. The main content area displays a chat log with the following text:

```
task_b.ipynb > M+ Task B > ↻ with open('combined_data...')
Next utterance please
Vorgang abbrechen.

faster printing speeds, and expanded design capabilities, pushing
--
?: Design for Additive Manufacturing-Element transitions and aggr
>: The design of additive manufacturing (AM) necessitates consider
smooth integration of different materials or geometries within a
printed components into a larger, more intricate final product.
optimizing build orientation to minimize material waste and impro
process parameters, and desired mechanical properties.
--
?: additive manufacturing
>: Additive manufacturing, commonly known as 3D printing, is a pr
material, additive manufacturing builds objects layer by layer.
sintering (SLS), each utilizing different materials like plastics
and consumer goods. Design for Additive Manufacturing considerati
--

You have already entered these 1 next utterances.
1 -- 3d printer additive
Now please enter the missing 9 ones.
```

3 1/3 Manual Runs

*"development of additive manufacturing",
"subtractive manufacturing",
"materials for 3D printing", ...*

*"3d filament uses fused deposition modeling",
"3d filament uses stereolithography",
"3d print selective laser sintering", ...*

*"cost of additive manufacturing",
"stability of 3d prints",
"pitfalls of additive manufacturing", ...*

*"Latest advancements in 3D printing for rapid
prototyping and customized products",
"Comparative analysis of FDM, SLA, and SLS 3D
printing technologies for industrial applications",
"Economic benefits and cost-effectiveness of
additive manufacturing adoption across
industries", ...*

- **Student 1:**
 - *A1 + A2*: Keep style of previous queries, query rewriting, including elements of interacted with documents whenever fitting
 - *B*: Keep style of previous queries, what did user learn from responses
- **Student 2:** *B*: Estimate knowledge of searcher from queries and results, asking ChatGPT for example queries
- **Student 3:** Consider previous queries + interacted with documents if content seemed relevant to queries
- **Student 4:** Translate last query to German with Google or Gemini web interface, Google suggestions of shortened query or topics in Google answers in next query, translate to English with Gemini

Automatic Runs

- Usage of small/cheap LLMs:
 - Gemini 2.0 flash
 - Gemini 2.5 flash
 - GPT 4.1 nano
- No differentiation between interaction types
- Same description of given data

You are required to return EXACTLY %NUMOFQUERIES% potential next queries, NOTHING ELSE. Queries need to be distinct from each other. Order them in descending order by probability of them being the next query. Return these next %NUMOFQUERIES% queries as a Python-style list. These are the previous queries (preceded by "\"?") as well as the corresponding received responses by the conversational system (preceded by "\">|

*"3D printing applications",
"3D printing materials",
"3D printing technologies", ...*

*"3D printing cost analysis",
"3D printing materials for beginners",
"3D printing troubleshooting guide", ...*

*"3D printing for gun parts",
"best 3D printer for hobbyists",
"3D printing metal parts cost", ...*

*"3D printing materials",
"3D printing applications",
"Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM) explained", ...*

10⁸/₃ Automatic Runs

- 8 runs on A1 only: Different prompts with instruction to follow chain-of-thought and mind context
- Consider interacted with documents/answer if relevant to previous query
- Completely unrelated new queries
- Trying to sell products in queries
- Language compatible with Gen Alpha
- Child-friendly language
- Expert user
- Natural sounding
- Working class user
- Racist user
- User part of several minorities

**Big thanks to my
student assistants!**

Agenda

9:00 - 9:15	Welcome	13:00-14:30	Workshop posters
9:15 - 10:00	Keynote by Christine Bauer	14:30-15:00	Overview talk on shared tasks & Lightning talks on shared tasks
10:00-10:30	Invited tech talks on toolkits and infrastructure pt 1	15:00-16:00	Breakout group discussions pt 1
10:30-11:00	<i>Coffee break</i>	16:00-16:30	<i>Coffee break</i>
11:00-12:00	Panel discussion	16:30-17:15	Breakout group discussions pt 2
12:00-12:30	Invited tech talks on toolkits and infrastructure pt 2	17:15-18:00	Reports of the group discussions and closing
12:30-14:00	<i>Lunch break</i>		

SIGIR Slack Channel: UserSim

#usersim

Breakout Group Discussions

Shared Task:

GROUP 2:

Reports on the Breakout Group Discussions

Breakout Group Discussions

Shared Task:

GROUP 2:

GROUP 3:

